

Upskilling Teachers Integration: Samr Practices for Transformation Instruction

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Abstract

This study assessed the level of ICT engagement in terms of cognitive-affective factors and the extent of ICT integration practice in English instruction using SAMR Model. The researcher used a descriptive-correlational research technique to determine the level of engagement and integration of ICT. The majority of the teachers were between the ages of 21 and 30, female, married, with 15 units in master's degree, have served 1-5 years and have attended school level training and seminars. The level of ICT engagement of the teachers in terms of cognitive-affective factors have sensed a strong agreement especially on their attitudes towards ICT. It clearly shows that they fully embrace and actively engage with ICT in their teaching. As to the extent of ICT integration using SAMR Model suggests that ICT integration among teachers falls within the "Advanced" category, with a stronger emphasis on Substitution and Augmentation rather than higher-order transformation through Modification and Redefinition. The study found a substantial correlation between conflict management styles in instruction and the school performance. The issues and concerns encountered by the respondents in integrating ICT are the following: technical issues and maintenance, lack of infrastructure, limited teacher training, high cost of technology, digital divide, resistance to change, time-consuming lesson preparation, distraction in learning and cybersecurity and privacy concerns.

Keywords: ICT, engagement, integration, SAMR, training plan, descriptive quantitative design, Mandaue City, Philippines.

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Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study

Since it has revolutionized teaching strategies and educational experiences, information and communication technology, or ICT, has emerged as a crucial element of contemporary education. Digital resources, learning management systems, and interactive whiteboards are examples of ICT technologies that improve education and encourage student participation (Bates, 2020). According

to Alismail and McGuire (2019), online learning systems such as Google Classroom and Moodle offer adaptable learning environments that accommodate a range of student demands and promote both collaborative and self-directed learning. Additionally, through virtual classrooms and free educational resources, ICT eliminates geographical obstacles and makes high-quality education accessible (UNESCO, 2021).

ICT integration in education has also transformed feedback and evaluation systems. With the use of data analytics, educators may use digital technologies to monitor students' progress in real time and modify their teaching methods to meet each student's unique learning needs (Selwyn, 2022). E-learning systems also provide formative and summative evaluations, which encourage ongoing learning by providing immediate feedback (Wang et al., 2020). ICT also makes adaptive learning systems possible, which modify content according to student performance, guaranteeing individualized learning experiences that improve academic success (Traxler, 2018).

Beyond instructional benefits, ICT fosters digital literacy and prepares students for the evolving workforce. As technology becomes integral to various industries, equipping learners with ICT skills enhances their employability and adaptability in the digital age (Voogt et al., 2018). Moreover, ICT supports global collaboration, enabling students to engage in cross-cultural exchanges and innovative projects through digital communication platforms (Redecker & Punie, 2017). However, while ICT offers numerous advantages, addressing challenges such as the digital divide and cybersecurity remains crucial for equitable and secure learning environments (OECD, 2021).

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in language teaching has become a global trend, transforming traditional classrooms into dynamic, interactive learning environments. The use of digital platforms, such as Duolingo, Rosetta Stone, and Babbel, has gained popularity worldwide, allowing learners to practice language skills through gamification and adaptive learning algorithms (Godwin-Jones, 2021). Additionally, artificial intelligence (AI)-powered chatbots and virtual assistants, like ChatGPT, provide personalized language learning experiences by offering instant feedback and conversation practice (Ziegler, 2022). In many countries, Learning Management Systems (LMS) such as Moodle and Blackboard facilitate blended learning approaches, combining face-to-face instruction with online resources to enhance student engagement and autonomy (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2021).

On a local scale, ICT integration in language teaching varies depending on access to digital infrastructure and educational policies. In the Philippines, for instance, the Department of Education (DepEd) has promoted the use of e-learning platforms such as DepEd Commons and Learning Resource Portal to support English language instruction, especially during the shift to remote learning (DepEd, 2021). Mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) is also a growing trend, with students utilizing smartphones and mobile applications to develop their reading, writing, listening, and speaking skills in both English and local languages (Bautista & Cornelio, 2020). Additionally, schools and universities increasingly use social media platforms like Facebook and YouTube for language learning activities, leveraging their accessibility and multimedia capabilities to foster student interaction and cultural exchange (Cabau, 2022).

Student learning outcomes and teaching effectiveness are greatly improved when information and communication technology (ICT) is included into English classroom. Students may improve their reading, writing, speaking, and listening abilities in fun and dynamic ways with digital resources including interactive whiteboards, multimedia presentations, and online learning platforms (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2021).

Moreover, ICT fosters authentic language use by exposing students to real-world English contexts through online communication, digital storytelling, and virtual exchanges with native speakers (Ziegler, 2022). Video conferencing tools such as Zoom and Microsoft Teams enable live

discussions, debates, and collaborative projects that improve students' confidence and fluency in English (Hampel & Stickler, 2021). Furthermore, artificial intelligence (AI)-powered tools like Grammarly and ChatGPT assist students in refining their writing skills by providing instant grammar and vocabulary suggestions (Chapelle & Sauro, 2020).

In addition, the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching strategies significantly enhances instructional effectiveness, student engagement, and overall efficiency in education. Digital tools such as interactive simulations, multimedia presentations, and e-learning platforms support diverse teaching methodologies, catering to different learning styles and improving knowledge retention (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2021). By encouraging active learning through gamification, virtual collaboration, and real-time evaluations, ICT also increases student engagement by making classes more participative and dynamic (Godwin-Jones, 2021). Additionally, technology simplifies administrative duties like lesson preparation and grading, freeing up instructors to concentrate more on individualized education and student assistance (Selwyn, 2022). Teachers may improve teaching and learning experiences by utilizing ICT to create more dynamic and inclusive learning environments.

Despite these advancements, challenges remain in the effective integration of ICT in language teaching, particularly in regions with limited technological resources. The digital divide, which refers to disparities in access to ICT tools and internet connectivity, affects the quality of language instruction, particularly in rural and underprivileged communities (Selwyn, 2022). Moreover, teacher training in ICT-based pedagogies remains a crucial factor in ensuring the effective use of technology in language learning (Hampel & Stickler, 2021). Future trends suggest an increasing reliance on artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and immersive learning experiences to further enhance language acquisition, making ICT an indispensable tool in modern language education worldwide (Godwin-Jones, 2023).

This research on ICT integration in teaching English is essential for understanding how digital tools enhance language instruction, student engagement, and overall learning outcomes. With the increasing reliance on technology in education, research in this field helps educators identify effective teaching strategies that incorporate multimedia, online platforms, and artificial intelligence to support language acquisition (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2021). Additionally, it provides insights into how ICT fosters interactive and student-centered learning, improving communication skills through real-world digital interactions and virtual collaborations (Ziegler, 2022). Research also highlights challenges such as the digital divide, teacher readiness, and accessibility, offering solutions for equitable and effective technology use in English instruction (Selwyn, 2022). Ultimately, studying ICT integration in English teaching informs policymaking, curriculum development, and teacher training programs, ensuring that technological advancements contribute meaningfully to language education. With this, the study focuses on ICT integration level of English teachers of Basak Elementary School, DepEd Mandaue City Division, Cebu, for the school year 2024-2025 as basis for training plan.

Theoretical Background

The research anchors the study on the following theories: Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006), SAMR Model (Puentedura, 2010), Constructivist Learning Theory (Piaget, 1972; Vygotsky, 1978), Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura) and Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller).

Three essential elements—technology, pedagogy, and subject knowledge—are balanced in the Technological Pedagogical subject Knowledge (TPACK) Framework, a theoretical model that describes how to successfully integrate technology into instruction (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). TPACK offers teachers an organized way to incorporate information and communication technology (ICT) into their teaching strategies when teaching English as a second language (ELT).

This paradigm highlights that instructors must possess both subject-matter competence and knowledge on how to use digital technologies to improve language learning. Teachers may provide dynamic and engaging learning environments that enhance student engagement and understanding by combining these three areas of knowledge (Chai et al., 2019).

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

In the Technological Knowledge (TK) component, teachers must be familiar with digital tools such as interactive whiteboards, language learning applications, and online platforms that support English instruction. Tools like Google Classroom, Duolingo, and Grammarly assist students in developing language skills through interactive exercises and automated feedback (Godwin-Jones, 2021). Additionally, artificial intelligence-powered tools such as ChatGPT help learners practice conversation and writing skills, making ICT a valuable asset in language acquisition (Ziegler, 2022). Without technological competence, teachers may struggle to integrate these resources effectively, highlighting the need for continuous professional development in ICT.

The Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) aspect of TPACK focuses on instructional strategies that align with technology use in ELT. Teachers must design student-centered learning experiences using ICT tools that promote engagement and interaction, such as discussion forums, collaborative writing platforms, and virtual language exchange programs (Hampel & Stickler, 2021). For example, integrating video conferencing for real-time discussions with native speakers enhances

listening and speaking skills. Additionally, flipped classroom models, where students engage with digital content before class discussions, allow for deeper analysis and practice in language learning (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2021).

The Content Knowledge (CK) component ensures that English language teachers understand the subject matter they are teaching and how technology can best support it. ICT tools must be used purposefully to enhance specific language skills such as grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary acquisition (Chapelle & Sauro, 2020). For instance, speech recognition software provides pronunciation feedback, while digital storytelling tools help students develop writing and creative expression. By integrating technology appropriately, teachers can facilitate authentic language use, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world communication (Stockwell & Hubbard, 2022).

The TPACK framework provides a comprehensive model for integrating ICT into English language teaching by balancing technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge. Effective ICT integration requires teachers to not only be proficient in digital tools but also to design meaningful learning experiences that align with language teaching objectives. However, challenges such as teacher training, technological infrastructure, and accessibility must be addressed to maximize the benefits of ICT in ELT (Selwyn, 2022). By applying TPACK principles, educators can enhance their teaching strategies, improve student learning outcomes, and prepare learners for communication in a digitally connected world.

Another theory anchored in this study is the SAMR Model, developed by Dr. Ruben Puentedura (2006), which provides a structured framework for integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education. It categorizes technology use into four levels: Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, and Redefinition. This model helps educators evaluate and enhance their use of digital tools in English language teaching (ELT), ensuring that technology is not merely an add-on but a transformative force in language instruction (Hamilton et al., 2016). By applying the SAMR Model, English teachers can progressively integrate ICT to improve student engagement, language acquisition, and communication skills.

At the Substitution level, technology acts as a direct replacement for traditional tools without changing the task. For instance, instead of using printed worksheets, teachers may provide digital PDFs for students to read and complete exercises (Romrell et al., 2014). Similarly, replacing physical dictionaries with online versions like Merriam-Webster or Google Translate serves as a basic integration of ICT in ELT. While substitution offers convenience, it does not significantly enhance the learning process, highlighting the need to move toward more advanced ICT applications.

The Augmentation stage involves adding functional improvements to traditional tasks through technology. In English teaching, this could mean using text-to-speech software to help students with pronunciation or incorporating interactive quizzes in Google Forms that provide instant feedback (Wang et al., 2020). Augmentation allows learners to engage with content in a more interactive way, enhancing their comprehension and motivation. For example, students writing essays can use grammar-checking tools like Grammarly to refine their writing skills, receiving automated feedback that improves accuracy and fluency (Godwin-Jones, 2021).

At the Modification level, technology significantly transforms learning activities, encouraging deeper engagement. English teachers can implement collaborative writing projects using cloud-based platforms such as Google Docs, where students co-edit essays in real time and provide peer feedback (Kirkland & O'Riordan, 2022). Another example is using video recording tools for students to create digital storytelling projects, improving their speaking skills and fostering creativity. By modifying traditional tasks, ICT enhances interaction, collaboration, and self-directed learning, making language instruction more effective.

Finally, the Redefinition stage involves the complete transformation of learning experiences, enabling activities that were previously impossible. The Augmentation stage involves adding functional improvements to traditional tasks through technology. In English teaching, this could mean using text-to-speech software to help students with pronunciation or incorporating interactive quizzes in Google Forms that provide instant feedback (Wang et al., 2020). Augmentation allows learners to engage with content in a more interactive way, enhancing their comprehension and motivation. For example, students writing essays can use grammar-checking tools like Grammarly to refine their writing skills, receiving automated feedback that improves accuracy and fluency (Godwin-Jones, 2021).

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For instance, English language learners can practice having real-time interactions with peers from other countries by taking part in international virtual exchanges using video conferencing systems such as Zoom (Hempel & Stickler, 2021). Furthermore, students may practice their English in simulated settings by using immersive technologies like virtual reality (VR), which imitate situations like placing an order at a restaurant or going to an international conference (Lindgren & Johnson-Glenberg, 2019). ICT promotes the development of advanced language abilities, cultural experience, and genuine language use through redefinition.

In conclusion, the SAMR Model serves as a valuable guide for integrating ICT in English language teaching, helping educators progress from basic technology substitution to transformative learning experiences. By gradually implementing more advanced levels of the model, teachers can enhance language instruction, promote active student participation, and prepare learners for communication in the digital age. However, to maximize the benefits of ICT, schools must ensure access to appropriate digital tools and provide professional development opportunities for educators (Selwyn, 2022). When applied effectively, the SAMR Model not only improves English teaching strategies but also fosters meaningful and engaging language learning experiences.

The Constructivist Learning Theory, developed by theorists such as Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, emphasizes that learners actively construct knowledge through experience and interaction rather than passively receiving information (Piaget, 1950; Vygotsky, 1978). In English language teaching (ELT), this theory promotes student-centered learning, where ICT tools facilitate authentic, interactive, and engaging language acquisition. Technology enables learners to explore language in meaningful contexts, collaborate with peers, and engage in self-directed learning, fostering deeper comprehension and retention (Jonassen, 1999). ICT integration, therefore, aligns with constructivist principles by transforming English instruction from a teacher-led approach to an inquiry-based, interactive process.

One of the key aspects of constructivist learning in ELT is collaborative learning, which effectively supports ICT tools. Online discussion forums, collaborative writing platforms like Google Docs, and social media encourage students to engage in peer-to-peer interaction, enhancing their communication skills (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2021). For instance, students working together on a shared document can co-construct knowledge by correcting each other's grammar, expanding vocabulary, and refining sentence structures. Additionally, video conferencing tools like Zoom and Microsoft Teams enable real-time conversations, allowing

students to practice speaking skills in an interactive and social learning environment (Hampel & Stickler, 2021).

Another constructivist principle that ICT enhances in ELT is learning through experience and immersion. Digital storytelling, role-playing games, and virtual reality (VR) applications provide contextualized language learning experiences that engage students in real-world communication (Lindgren & Johnson-Glenberg, 2019). For example, students can create digital narratives using tools like Storybird or practice conversational English in virtual simulations that mimic real-life situations such as ordering food or conducting interviews (Godwin-Jones, 2021). These immersive experiences make language learning more meaningful and encourage students to actively apply their linguistic knowledge.

ICT also supports scaffolded learning, a core principle of Vygotsky's constructivist approach, by providing tools that guide students at different proficiency levels. Adaptive learning platforms such as Duolingo and Rosetta Stone adjust language exercises based on individual performance, offering targeted feedback to help learners progress at their own pace (Stockwell & Hubbard, 2022). Furthermore, students may improve their writing abilities while gaining contextual explanations from AI-powered writing aides such as Grammarly, which offer real-time grammar corrections and recommendations (Chapelle & Sauro, 2020). By serving as scaffolds, these ICT resources enable students to progressively improve their language skills and expand on their existing knowledge.

Constructivist Learning Theory aligns well with ICT integration in English language teaching, as technology fosters interactive, experiential, and student-centered learning. By leveraging digital tools, educators can create meaningful language learning experiences that encourage collaboration, immersion, and personalized learning. To guarantee that technology is utilized efficiently to support constructivist teaching concepts, its implementation necessitates meticulous instructional design and teacher training (Selwyn, 2022). In order to prepare students for real-world communication in a digitally linked society, ICT's role in supporting constructivist methods in ELT will continue to be vital as it develops.

Moreover, the significance of modeling, imitation, and observational learning in human behavior and cognitive development is emphasized by Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (SCT). When incorporating ICT into English instruction, SCT promotes the notion that children may pick up language skills by watching classmates, instructors, and digital role models in addition to receiving direct instruction. Students can learn more effectively through modeling when they see and hear language use in real-world situations, such as through interactive simulations, language applications, or films. ICT may provide an engaging environment where learners actively generate knowledge and practice English in meaningful ways, according to Bandura's idea of reciprocal determinism, which describes the interaction between personal variables, behavior, and environmental effects.

Furthermore, John Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) highlights the significance of working memory management during learning and describes how the human brain absorbs information. CLT acts as a guide for creating instructional materials that don't overwhelm students when incorporating information and communication technology (ICT) into English teaching and learning. Digital tools should provide information in a clear, organized manner that minimizes unnecessary cognitive burden because working memory has a limited capacity. For example, if multimedia tools adhere to concepts like the modality effect or coherence principle, they can improve understanding by combining text with audio or visual signals. This makes it easier to acquire vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension skills more quickly.

Along with these theories, this research also anchors the following legal basis: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) – Goal 4 (Quality Education) (United Nations, 2015), UNESCO ICT

Competency Framework for Teachers (ICT CFT) (2018), Republic Act No. 10533 (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013), DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), DepEd Order No. 78, s. 2010 DepEd Computerization Program.

At the global level, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) – Goal 4 (Quality Education) highlight the importance of inclusive and quality education, advocating for the use of technology to enhance teaching and learning. Similarly, the UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers (ICT-CFT) provides a structured approach to developing teachers' ICT competencies, ensuring they can effectively integrate digital tools into their pedagogy.

At the national level, in the Philippines, various laws and policies mandate ICT integration in teaching. Republic Act No. 10533, or the Enhanced Basic Education Act (K-12 Law), requires the incorporation of 21st-century skills, including ICT literacy, in the curriculum. This law emphasizes the need for English teachers to integrate technology-driven instructional methods such as digital storytelling, multimedia presentations, and interactive language exercises. A thorough plan for integrating ICT in education is also provided by the DepEd Computerization Program (DepEd Order No. 78, s. 2010), which offers recommendations for teacher preparation programs to enhance digital literacy. In order to improve English instruction, this project encourages the use of e-learning platforms, educational applications, and online resources. The last one is DepEd Order 50 s. assist the Department's objective of continuously retraining and upskilling educators and school administrators to improve learning outcomes by 2020.

These legal bases establish a strong foundation for upskilling teachers in ICT integration for English instruction, ensuring that educators are equipped with the necessary digital competencies to enhance their teaching methods. By aligning with these frameworks, training programs can better support teachers in adopting innovative, technology-driven approaches that improve student engagement, language acquisition, and overall learning outcomes in English education.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

This research assessed the level of competence of English teachers in the integration and engagement in terms of cognitive-affective factors in ICT of Basak Elementary School, DepEd Mandaue City Division, Cebu for the school year 2024-2025 as a basis for a training plan.

Specifically, this answered the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teacher respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age and gender,
 - 1.2 civil status
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment,
 - 1.4 years in service, and
 - 1.5 relevant training/ seminar /workshop attended?
2. As perceived by the teacher respondents, what is the level of ICT engagement in teaching-learning in terms of cognitive-affective factors:
 - 2.1 attitude,
 - 2.2 perception, and
 - 2.3 skills?

3. As perceived by the teacher respondents', what is the extent of ICT integration through SAMR practices as to:
 - 3.1 substitution,
 - 3.2 augmentation,
 - 3.3, modification, and
 - 3.4 redefinition?
4. Is there a significant correlation between the level of engagement in teaching-learning in terms of cognitive-affective factors and ICT integration through SAMR practices?
5. What are the issues and concerns encountered by the teacher respondents' in integrating ICT in teaching English?
6. Based on findings, what training plan can be developed?

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the level of engagement in teaching-learning in terms of cognitive-affective factors and ICT integration through SAMR practices. The null hypothesis given was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Significance of the Study

This study is beneficial for the following:

Department of Education. The findings can inform policy development, curriculum revisions, and teacher training programs, ensuring that ICT integration aligns with national education goals. Additionally, it helps DepEd assess the effectiveness of its existing ICT-based educational programs and make necessary improvements.

The Administrators. The findings can guide them in allocating resources, implementing professional development programs, and improving digital infrastructure in schools. This study will help them create a supportive environment where technology-enhanced teaching and learning can thrive.

School heads. In order to design successful ICT upskilling programs and track their effects on English education, this research offers data-driven suggestions. The findings will assist school administrators in formulating plans to inspire educators and cultivate a culture of technologically driven creativity in the classroom.

Teachers. This provides practical solutions to improve their ICT skills and teaching methodologies. By identifying specific challenges and best practices, the study can help teachers develop digital competencies, enhance their instructional strategies, and increase student engagement through technology.

Learners. Students will experience improved learning outcomes and engagement as teachers enhance their ability to integrate technology into English instruction.

Society/Community. The study contributes to developing digitally literate students who can effectively communicate and compete in a globalized world. Additionally, communities benefit from schools that embrace digital transformation, as these institutions can extend learning opportunities through online platforms and community-based digital literacy programs.

The Researcher. This study provides an opportunity for the researcher to contribute to the body of knowledge on ICT integration in education. It allows the researcher to explore educational technology trends, instructional strategies, and policy implications, ultimately contributing to the advancement of teacher training programs.

Future researchers. The findings of this study can serve as a reference for future studies on ICT integration in education. It provides a foundation for exploring related topics, such as the effectiveness of specific digital tools in English instruction, the long-term impact of ICT training on teaching quality, and the role of artificial intelligence in language learning.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This part contains the research methodology which includes the method used, the flow of the study, research locale, research respondents, research instruments, data gathering procedures, statistical treatment of data, scoring procedures and definition of terms.

Design

The study used a descriptive-survey research design to collect assess the level of ICT integration using the SAMR model and their engagement in terms of cognitive-affective factors of the English teachers of Basak Elementary School, DepEd Mandaue City Division, Cebu. The design was deemed appropriate for the study since the research instrument is survey-based. The statistical methods that were used include the percentage, frequency, weighted mean, standard deviation, and Pearson correlation. Additionally, a significant relationship between the variables was found, increasing the design's applicability.

Flow of the Study

The flow of the research followed the system approach of input, process, and output. The needed data on the input were the profile data of English teachers such as age, civil status, gender, highest educational attainment, years in service, relevant trainings/seminars attended.

Moreover, the input consists of the related information that was adopted to be able to acquire the required information on: (1) level of ICT integration using the SAMR model, (2) ICT engagement in terms of cognitive-affective factors (3) relevance between the level of ICT integration and their engagement.

Finding participating respondents was the first phase in the study's pre-data collection process, from which the data was collected. The next steps were creating the questionnaire and writing letters to the principal requesting permission to carry out the study. The responders received an online access to the questionnaire via Google Form after the letter has been authorized.

The respondents who were chosen at random were given a survey questionnaire, which would be used to gather data. The four components of the device were intended to collect data. By highlighting the voluntary nature of the study and anonymizing replies, the researcher protects confidentiality while facilitating participation.

After that, data was gathered and sent to the statistician for analysis. With the research adviser's help, it undergone additional presentation, analysis, and interpretation. A training plan was suggested in light of the findings and outcomes.

Figure 2. Flow of the Study

Environment

The researcher conducted this research in Basak Elementary School, one of the north district schools in the Division of Mandaue City. worked diligently to secure a plot of land large enough to build a primary school.

Figure 3. Location of the Environment

Basak Elementary School. Basak Elementary School was established in 1921 through the efforts of Mr. Anastacio Perez, Julio and Domingo Alinsug, and Clemente Paran, who The school's first teacher and principal, Eriberto Dimpas, who later became the 6th External Mayor of Mandaue, initially taught a combined class of 60 students from Grades I and II. As more students advanced, the school expanded to accommodate intermediate grade levels.

Although the late Mayor Dimpas only completed high school at Cebu Provincial High School, he was able to develop competent students during his time as an educator. Located in Basak,

Mandaue City, the school has grown into a key educational institution in the North District. Due to increasing enrollment, more teachers were assigned to serve learners from both the local community and nearby Barangay. Over the years, Basak Elementary School has become one of the largest schools in the division. Its strategic location near public transportation also led to its designation as the North District’s central school.

More than 3,000 students are now enrolled in classes at Basak Elementary School, which offers Special Education (SPED) as well as Kindergarten through Grade VI. One principal, one deputy principal, and 101 teachers work at the school. With scientific programs offered at every school level, it offers a comprehensive elementary education. A fully complete Learning Resource Center, Science Laboratories, Kindergarten Playroom, canteens, and libraries are just a few of the resources the school offers to enhance student learning. With the help of these materials, students are guaranteed access to a vibrant and stimulating learning environment.

Guided by the principle of "Education for All," Basak Elementary School upholds the Department of Education’s mission to provide inclusive, equitable, and quality education, ensuring that every learner has the opportunity to grow, explore, and succeed.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 30 English teachers of Basak Elementary School.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Respondent Groups	Frequency	Percentage
English Teachers	30	100
Total	30	100

Instrument

The instruments were divided into three parts: a profile of the respondents, a survey form on ICT integration based on SAMR model and ICT engagement.

The first part of the questionnaire was the demographic profile of the respondents which included their age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in service, number of relevant trainings/ seminars/workshops attended, position and rating for overall accomplishment.

The second and third components were on ICT integration based on SAMR model and ICT engagement. The tool that was used in gathering the data for the ICT integration is from Dwiono, R., Rochsantiningih, D., & Suparno, S. (2018) entitled, “Investigating the Integration Level of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the English Language Teaching”. The ICT engagement questionnaire was taken from the study of Muslem et al. (2018), entitled, “Perceptions and Barriers to ICT Use Among English Teachers In Indonesia”.

Data Gathering

First, an approval letter addressed to the School Head of Basak Elementary School was sent seeking approval to conduct the study.

The responders got the questionnaire in person after the letter has been authorized. There was a plenty of time for the responders to complete the questionnaire—ideally 20 to 30 minutes. They were offered surveys via their chosen online platforms if they would rather complete them that way.

The statistician received the data when it has been gathered and processed statistically. After then, it undergone additional presentation, analysis, and interpretation under the direction of the research adviser.

A final draft was sent in for editing and finalization.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Simple Percentage Analysis. It was used to determine the link between the provided data by comparing two or more informational arrangements.

Weighted Mean. This is an average in which the relative importance of each observation is established by giving each of its distinct values a weight. Multiplying the number of responses by the predetermined weights yields the sum of the computed values.

Pearson-r. This was utilized to determine the significant relationship on the level of engagement in teaching-learning in terms of cognitive-affective factors and ICT integration through SAMR practices.

Standard Deviation. A collection of data values' variability was examined using this statistical method. It aided in figuring out how dispersed the data points were from the mean, which shows the dataset's consistency or variability.

Scoring Procedure

Scoring Procedure for ICT Engagement

Weight	Scale	Category	Verbal Description
5	4.20- 5.00	Strongly Agree	I fully embrace and actively engage with ICT in my teaching.
4	3.40- 4.19	Agree	I generally engage with ICT and see its benefits in education.
3	2.60- 3.39	Neutral	I am somewhat engaged with ICT but have no strong feelings about it.
2	1.80- 2.59	Disagree	I am hesitant to use ICT and do not find it very useful.
1	1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree	I avoid using ICT and believe it does not enhance my teaching.

Scoring Procedures for ICT integration

Weight	Scale	Category	Verbal Description
5	4.20- 5.00	Fully Expert	I consistently integrate ICT to transform English language teaching, enabling student-centered and interactive learning experiences.
4	3.40- 4.19	Expert	I regularly use ICT tools to enhance English instruction, improving engagement and learning outcomes.
3	2.60- 3.39	Advance	I sometimes incorporate ICT into my English lessons but rely on traditional methods as well.
2	1.80- 2.59	Intermediate	I use ICT occasionally, but it is not a central part of my teaching strategy.
1	1.00-1.79	Novice	I rarely or never use ICT in teaching English.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

For better understanding and clarity, and to establish standard construction of meaning, the following terms had been given both conceptual and operational definitions:

Affective. Represents the emotional response and personal feelings toward ICT use. This includes motivation, enthusiasm, and enjoyment in engaging with ICT tools, as well as anxiety or resistance to technology.

Attitude. Encompasses an individual's overall disposition or stance toward ICT, whether positive or negative. This includes openness to learning new technologies, confidence in using ICT tools, and the readiness to integrate them into daily activities.

Augmentation. Provides a technological improvement for a task that could be completed without technology.

Capability-building program. A planned program created to increase people's or organizations' knowledge, abilities, and competences in order to boost their performance and efficacy in ICT integration.

Cognitive. Referring to the mental operations required to comprehend, evaluate, and use ICT tools and technology. When utilizing ICT for a variety of tasks, it involves problem-solving, critical thinking, and decision-making.

ICT. Refers to all digital tools, systems, and resources used to manage, process, and communicate information.

ICT integration. The process of embedding ICT tools into various activities, especially in education, to enhance efficiency, engagement, and productivity.

Modification. Enables the substantial modification of a current activity in a manner that is not achievable without technology.

Perception. Refers to how people perceive and understand ICT, including their opinions regarding its applicability, usability, and importance in their personal or professional lives. The propensity to embrace and use technology is influenced by perception.

Redefinition. The creation of a completely new task is not possible without the technology.

Skills. Refers to the ability to effectively and efficiently use ICT tools and applications. This includes basic digital literacy, technical proficiency, and advanced competencies such as programming, data analysis, or cybersecurity.

SAMR Model. It is a framework used to integrate technology into education and other fields, describing different levels of technology adoption.

Substitution. The application of technology to a task that might be completed without it.

Chapter 2

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS OF DATA AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the data obtained from the respondents, composed mainly of school heads and teachers. It answers the questions posed in the problem. The study was divided into three parts. The first part of the chapter deals with related information as to teachers' age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in service, number of trainings, seminars, and workshops attended. The second part of the study deals with the level of ICT engagement and ICT integration. The third part discusses the significant relationship between ICT engagement and integration and the issues and concerns affecting the mentioned variables.

RELEVANT INFORMATION

This initial section manages the respondents’ important information of the teachers of Basak Elementary School.

Teachers

This section pertains to the relevant information of English teacher respondents in terms of age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in the service, seminars and workshops attended.

Age

Age diversity fosters a dynamic learning environment where innovation and experience intersect. English teachers across different age groups bring unique perspectives to ICT integration and engagement. Table 2 presents the distribution of the teacher-respondents in terms of age.

Table 2. Age Profile of the Teachers

Variable	Teachers	
	F	Percentage
51-60 years old	2	6.67
41-50 years old	4	13.33
31-40 years old	8	26.67
21-30 years old	16	53.33
Total	30	100.00
Mean	32.83	
SD	0.931	

Table 2 presents the age distribution of teachers, highlighting the concentration of educators within different age brackets. The majority of teachers (53.33%) belong to the 21-30 age group, followed by 26.67% in the 31-40 age category. This indicates that a significant portion of the teaching workforce is relatively young, suggesting a dynamic and potentially adaptable teaching environment.

Meanwhile, 13.33% of the teachers fall within the 41-50 age range, and only 6.67% are aged 51-60. This relatively low percentage of older teachers may imply a workforce that is still in its early to mid-career stages, with fewer veteran educators. The mean age of the teachers is 32.83 years, with a standard deviation of 0.931, further reinforcing that the majority are in their early thirties.

Overall, the age profile reflects a teaching workforce that is predominantly youthful, which could impact instructional methods, teacher retention, and professional development initiatives within the institution.

Age can significantly impact teachers' ICT integration. Studies indicate that younger teachers often exhibit greater proficiency and confidence in using technology compared to their older counterparts. For instance, research by Ibrahim et al. (2024) found that younger Albanian science teachers were more comfortable incorporating ICT into their teaching processes. Similarly, Napal et al. (2018) observed a negative correlation between teachers' digital competence and age, suggesting that older teachers may require additional support to effectively integrate ICT.

Gender

Gender is a significant element that has to be investigated. This establishes the sex—male or female. Table 3 shows the gender breakdown of respondents who are teachers.

Table 3 presents the gender distribution of teachers, showing a significant gender disparity. The majority of the teaching staff are female, comprising 86.67% of the total workforce, while only

13.33% are male. This indicates that the teaching profession in this setting is predominantly female dominated.

Table 3. Gender Profile of the Teachers

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Male	4	13.33
Female	26	86.67
Total	30	100

Gender differences also play a role in ICT engagement among teachers. Some studies suggest that male teachers may have higher confidence in using technology, while female teachers might face more challenges due to societal and cultural factors. However, these findings are not universal, and the influence of gender on ICT integration can vary across different contexts. For example, research by Bariham (2019) highlighted that teacher characteristics such as gender and age impact technology integration in educational settings.

Civil Status

Civil status is an additional pertinent consideration. The respondents' marital status indicates whether they are single or married. In terms of their civil status, the profile of the teacher responders is shown in Table 4.

The data in Table 4 shows that 17 teachers (56.67%) are married, while 13 teachers (43.33%) are single. This indicates that the majority of the teachers are married, making up more than half of the workforce. However, a significant portion remains single, accounting for nearly half of the total teaching staff.

Table 4. Civil Status of the Teachers

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Single	13	43.33
Married	17	56.67
Total	30	100

The relationship between civil status and ICT integration is less explored in recent literature. While some studies suggest that personal commitments associated with marital status might influence the time and energy teachers can devote to professional development in ICT, comprehensive research specifically addressing this variable remains limited.

Highest Educational Attainment

Among the factors that need to be considered is the highest degree of education. This relates to what level of education that the respondents, who are teachers, have attained. Table 5 presents the profile of the respondents based on their greatest degree of schooling.

The data in Table 5 shows the highest educational attainment of the teachers. The majority, 14 teachers (46.67%), have earned 15 units in a master's degree in education, indicating that many are pursuing further studies. 7 teachers (23.33%) hold a bachelor's degree (BSED/BEED) as their highest qualification, while 5 teachers (16.67%) have completed the Certificate of Academic Requirements for a master's degree.

Table 5. Highest Educational Attainment of the Teachers

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
With units in Doctorate Degree of Education	1	3.33
Full – fledged master's degree of Education	3	10.00

With Certificate of Academic Requirements of Education	5	16.67
With 15 units in master's degree of Education	14	46.67
Bachelor's Degree (BSED/BEED)	7	23.33
Total	30	100.00

Additionally, 3 teachers (10.00%) have obtained a full-fledged master's degree in education, and only 1 teacher (3.33%) has taken units in a Doctorate Degree of Education. This distribution reflects a faculty where a significant number are continuing their professional development through postgraduate studies.

A teacher's educational background, particularly in relation to prior exposure to technology, significantly affects their ability to integrate ICT into teaching. Teachers with formal education or training in technology-related fields are generally more adept at utilizing ICT tools. The study by Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2015) emphasizes that well-prepared teachers with adequate ICT knowledge can effectively enhance the teaching and learning process.

Number of Years in the Service

The number of years in the teacher is another crucial consideration in this study. Their loyalty to the company they now work for may be determined by the duration of their service. The number of years in service is displayed in Table 6.

Table 6. Number of Years in Service of the Teachers

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
16 – 20 yrs.	1	3.33
11 – 15 yrs.	4	13.33
6 – 10 yrs.	5	16.67
1-5 yrs.	20	66.67
Total	30	100.00
Mean	5.67	
SD	4.23	

The data in Table 6 presents the number of years in service of the teachers. The majority, 20 teachers (66.67%), have 1 to 5 years of experience, indicating that most of the faculty members are relatively new in the profession. 5 teachers (16.67%) have served for 6 to 10 years, while 4 teachers (13.33%) have 11 to 15 years of experience. Only 1 teacher (3.33%) has been in service for 16 to 20 years, representing the most experienced educator in the group.

The mean year of service is 5.67, with a standard deviation of 4.23, highlighting the predominance of early-career teachers within the institution.

Teaching experience plays a nuanced role in ICT integration. Some studies suggest that more experienced teachers may exhibit reluctance toward adopting new technologies, possibly due to established routines or apprehension about technological complexities. Conversely, less experienced teachers might be more open to integrating ICT, reflecting a greater familiarity with digital tools. For instance, a study by Laabidi (2022) found that teaching experience and age significantly influenced professors' use of ICT in their teaching processes. Similarly, research by Magallanes et al. (2024) indicated that factors such as age and teaching experience significantly influence teachers' proficiency and their perceptions of the benefits of ICT integration in physical education instruction.

Relevant Trainings and Seminar Attended

English instructors who get ongoing professional development through ICT-related training are more prepared to successfully use technology into their lessons. In digital classrooms, exposure to such applications promotes self-assurance, creativity, and flexibility. Table 7 presents the appropriate training, seminars, and workshops attended by the respondents.

The data in Table 7 shows the distribution of trainings, seminars, and workshops attended by teachers. The majority, 18 teachers (60.00%), have participated in school-based trainings, indicating that most professional development activities take place within the institution. 5 teachers (16.67%) have attended regional trainings, while 3 teachers (10.00%) have participated in both national and division-level seminars.

Table 7. Trainings, Seminars, and Workshop Attended

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
International	1	3.33
National	3	10.00
Regional	5	16.67
Division	3	10.00
School	18	60.00
Total	30	100.00

Only 1 teacher (3.33%) has attended an international training, showing limited exposure to global professional development opportunities. The data suggests that while most teachers have engaged in local or school-based training, fewer have had opportunities for higher-level professional development at national and international levels.

Participation in ICT-related seminars and training programs is crucial for effective technology integration. Continuous professional development helps teachers stay updated with evolving technologies and pedagogical strategies. The systematic review by Alzakwani et al. (2025) underscores the importance of digital competencies in teacher professional development and highlights the need for ongoing ICT education to address existing inadequacies.

ICT ENGAGEMENT AND INTERGRATION

The second part of the study deals with the ICT engagement and integration of English teachers in Basak Elementary School.

Attitude

A positive attitude toward ICT integration enhances motivation and willingness to adopt technology for learning and work efficiency. Encouraging openness to digital tools fosters innovation and adaptability in an increasingly technology-driven world. The assessment of teachers' attitude towards ICT engagement is presented in Table 8

Table 8. Attitude

Indicators	WM	SD	VI
1. I believe that integrating ICT into teaching enhances student learning.	5.00	0.405	SA
2. I enjoy exploring new ICT tools and applications for classroom instruction.	4.60	0.345	SA
3. I feel confident using ICT in my teaching practices.	4.30	0.310	SA
4. I see ICT as an essential component of 21st-century education.	4.90	0.389	SA

5. I believe that ICT makes my teaching more efficient and effective.	5.00	0.405	SA
6. I see ICT as a positive tool for enhancing student engagement.	4.90	0.389	SA
7. I am willing to experiment with different ICT tools to find the best fit for my teaching style.	4.60	0.345	SA
8. I believe that ICT helps me connect better with my students.	4.80	0.374	SA
9. I feel comfortable adapting to changes in ICT tools and educational technology.	4.60	0.345	SA
10. I trust that my students benefit from my use of ICT in the classroom.	4.80	0.374	SA
Average Mean	4.75	0.368	SA

Legend

4.20- 5.00 Strongly Agree 2.60-3.39 Neutral 1.00-1.79 Strongly Disagree

3.40- 4.19 Agree 1.80-2.59 Disagree

The data in Table 8 presents teachers' attitudes toward integrating ICT into teaching and learning. The highest-ranked indicators, with a weighted mean (WM) of 5.00 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.405, highlight teachers' strong belief that ICT enhances student learning and makes teaching more efficient and effective. This suggests that educators perceive ICT as a crucial tool in improving the quality of instruction and facilitating better learning outcomes.

Following closely, two indicators—viewing ICT as an essential component of 21st-century education and as a positive tool for enhancing student engagement—both received a WM of 4.90 with an SD of 0.389, ranking third. These responses indicate a strong consensus that ICT plays a significant role in modern pedagogy, emphasizing its relevance in fostering interactive and engaging learning experiences. Similarly, the belief that ICT helps teachers connect better with students and ensures that students benefit from its use garnered a WM of 4.80 and an SD of 0.374, ranking fifth, further reinforcing the perception that ICT bridges communication gaps and enhances learning interactions.

The willingness to experiment with different ICT tools, confidence in adapting to changes in educational technology, and enjoyment in exploring new ICT applications all received a WM of 4.60 with an SD of 0.345, ranking seventh.

This demonstrates that while teachers are open to incorporating ICT into their instruction, there may be varying levels of expertise or experience influencing their confidence in using technology. Notably, the lowest-ranked statement, with a WM of 4.30 and an SD of 0.310, pertains to teachers' confidence in using ICT in their teaching practices, indicating that while attitudes are highly positive, some teachers may still face challenges in fully integrating technology into their pedagogical approach.

Overall, the average mean score of 4.75 (SD = 0.368) reflects a strong agreement among teachers regarding the positive impact of ICT in education. This suggests a highly favorable attitude toward technology, with most educators recognizing its significance in modern teaching. However, the variation in rankings implies that while enthusiasm for ICT is widespread, certain areas, such as confidence in usage, may require additional training and support to maximize its potential in classroom instruction.

Attitude towards ICT significantly affects its integration and utilization in education. A study by Bicen et al. (2023) examined the impact of student attitudes on information, communication, and

creation skills, revealing those positive attitudes towards ICT correlate with enhanced student engagement and skill development.

Perception

Perception of ICT as a valuable and user-friendly resource influences its effective adoption in education. When individuals see technology as beneficial, they are more likely to engage with and maximize its potential. Table 9 shows the assessment of teacher's perception on ICT engagement.

Table 9. Perception

Indicators	WM	SD	VI
1. In my view, ICTs are more powerful in teaching than discussion and teaching without the use of ICT.	4.30	0.310	SA
2. ICTs (referring generally to computers, videos, hardware, software, and networks) increase my knowledge and skills as an English teacher.	4.70	0.359	SA
3. ICTs are highly needed by teachers in teaching English.	4.50	0.333	SA
4. ICTs can be used as advanced instructional tools in teaching English to my students.	4.70	0.359	SA
5. In my view, ICTs can replace teacher in teaching English.	2.80	0.337	N
6. As far as I know, ICTs can be used to effectively manipulate instructional content and materials.	4.60	0.345	SA
7. I know that ICTs can spread knowledge and information fast.	4.70	0.359	SA
8. I use/have used ICTs for teaching and in daily life.	4.50	0.333	SA
9. In my view ICTs can be used as curriculum materials at school.	4.10	0.293	A
10. In my view, ICTs are more effective for teaching and learning than books and other printed materials.	4.20	0.301	SA
Average Mean	4.31	0.333	SA

The data in Table 9 presents teachers' perceptions of ICT in teaching English. The highest-ranked indicators, with a weighted mean (WM) of 4.70 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.359, highlight the perception that ICT increases teachers' knowledge and skills, serves as an advanced instructional tool, and spreads knowledge and information quickly. These results indicate a strong consensus among educators that ICT significantly enhances their professional development and instructional capabilities, making it a valuable resource in English language teaching.

Following closely, the belief that ICTs can effectively manipulate instructional content and materials received a WM of 4.60 (SD = 0.345), ranking fourth. This suggests that teachers recognize the versatility of ICT in improving the delivery of lessons and customizing learning materials to fit students' needs. Similarly, the necessity of ICT in teaching English and its frequent use in daily life and instruction both garnered a WM of 4.50 (SD = 0.333), ranking fifth. These findings reinforce the idea that ICT is not only beneficial but also an integral part of modern teaching methodologies.

The perception that ICT is more powerful in teaching than traditional discussions and non-ICT methods ranked seventh, with a WM of 4.30 (SD = 0.310). This implies that while teachers acknowledge the advantages of ICT, they may still value conventional teaching strategies. The belief that ICTs are more effective than books and printed materials ranked eighth, with a WM of 4.20 (SD = 0.301), indicating a preference for digital resources but not necessarily a complete replacement of traditional learning materials. Interestingly, the perception that ICT can serve as

curriculum material received a slightly lower rating (WM = 4.10, SD = 0.293), ranking ninth, suggesting that while ICT is seen as beneficial, there may be reservations about fully integrating it into the curriculum.

The lowest-ranked indicator, with a WM of 2.80 (SD = 0.337), pertains to the perception that ICT can replace teachers in teaching English. This neutral response suggests that while ICT is valued as a teaching tool, educators do not view it as a substitute for human instruction. Overall, the average mean score of 4.31 (SD = 0.333) reflects a strong agreement on the importance of ICT in teaching English, highlighting its role in enhancing knowledge, instructional delivery, and access to information, while also acknowledging the continued relevance of traditional teaching methods.

Perception of ICT's effectiveness influences its adoption and integration. Research by Tejedor et al. (2023) analyzed university teaching staff's perceptions of ICT's capacity to meet diverse student needs. The study found that positive perceptions of ICT efficacy are associated with increased adoption and proactive use in addressing various educational requirements.

Skills

Developing ICT skills equips individuals with the competencies needed to navigate digital platforms effectively. Strong digital literacy enhances productivity, problem-solving, and lifelong learning in a tech-centric society. The evaluation of teachers skills in ICT engagement is presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Skills

Indicators	WM	SD	VI
1. I am confident in using basic ICT tools (e.g., word processors, spreadsheets, presentation software) for teaching.	4.10	0.293	A
2. I can effectively integrate ICT tools into my lesson plans to enhance student learning.	4.00	0.286	A
3. I am skilled in using online learning platforms (e.g., Google Classroom, Moodle, Microsoft Teams) for instructional purposes.	4.10	0.293	A
4. I can troubleshoot minor technical issues with ICT tools and applications in my classroom.	3.80	0.278	A
5. I am proficient in using digital assessment tools (e.g., online quizzes, automated grading, learning analytics) to evaluate student performance.	3.90	0.281	A
6. I can create engaging multimedia content (e.g., videos, animations, interactive presentations) to support my lessons.	3.90	0.281	A
7. I am comfortable using ICT for differentiated instruction to cater to students' diverse learning needs.	4.50	0.333	SA
8. I regularly update my ICT skills through professional development activities (e.g., workshops, webinars, self-learning).	3.80	0.278	A
9. I am confident in using online communication platforms (e.g., emails, forums, messaging apps) to engage with students and parents.	4.80	0.374	SA
10. I am confident that my ICT skills positively impact student engagement and learning outcomes.	4.60	0.345	SA
Average Mean	4.15	0.290	A

The data in Table 10 presents teachers' self-assessed ICT skills in relation to teaching and learning. The highest-ranked indicator, with a weighted mean (WM) of 4.80 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.374, reflects teachers' confidence in using online communication platforms such as emails, forums, and messaging apps to engage with students and parents. This suggests that educators feel most proficient in leveraging digital communication tools to facilitate interaction and collaboration.

Following closely, the second-highest indicator, with a WM of 4.60 (SD = 0.345), highlights the confidence that ICT skills positively impact student engagement and learning outcomes. This signifies that teachers recognize the effectiveness of their technological competencies in fostering a more interactive and engaging learning environment. Similarly, comfort in using ICT for differentiated instruction ranked third, with a WM of 4.50 (SD = 0.333), indicating that many teachers feel capable of adapting ICT tools to address diverse student learning needs.

The ability to use basic ICT tools such as word processors, spreadsheets, and presentation software, as well as proficiency in using online learning platforms, both received a WM of 4.10 (SD = 0.293), ranking fourth. This suggests that while teachers are generally adept at handling fundamental digital tools, there may still be room for further development. The ability to integrate ICT into lesson plans ranked sixth, with a WM of 4.00 (SD = 0.286), indicating that while teachers recognize the importance of ICT integration, some may need more support or experience in applying it effectively.

With a WM of 3.90 (SD = 0.281), the capacity to apply digital assessment tools and produce captivating multimedia content came in seventh place, indicating a modest level of confidence in using these resources for teaching. With a WM of 3.80 (SD = 0.278), the lowest-ranked indicators are resolving minor technical problems and routinely upgrading ICT skills through professional development. This implies that even while instructors are proficient in ICT, they could find it difficult to fix technical issues and stay up to date with changing technological trends.

Overall, the average mean score of 4.15 (SD = 0.290) falls within the "Agree" category, indicating that while teachers possess a solid foundation in ICT skills, there is still a need for continuous professional development to enhance their proficiency, particularly in troubleshooting, multimedia creation, and digital assessment.

Proficiency in ICT skills is essential for meaningful engagement. A study by Tondeur et al. (2022) highlighted that students' digital literacy and self-efficacy are significant predictors of online learning engagement. The research emphasized the importance of developing digital competencies to enhance self-efficacy and foster active participation in online learning environments.

Summary on ICT Engagement

Table 11 shows the summary of the weighted means of the ICT engagement in terms of cognitive-affective factors.

Table 11. Level of ICT Engagement on Cognitive-Affective Factors

Variables	WM	SD	VI
Attitude	4.75	0.368	SA
Perception	4.13	0.333	SA
Skills	4.15	0.290	S
Average Weighted Mean	4.34	0.330	SA

The data in Table 13 presents an overview of teachers' cognitive-affective factors related to ICT, encompassing attitude, perception, and skills. Among these factors, attitude ranks the highest with a weighted mean (WM) of 4.75 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.368, interpreted as "Strongly Agree." This indicates that teachers have a highly positive outlook on the role and impact of ICT

in education, demonstrating enthusiasm and acceptance of technology integration in teaching and learning.

The second-ranked factor, skills, has a WM of 4.15 (SD = 0.290), interpreted as "Strongly Agree" (SA). This suggests that teachers feel confident in their ability to utilize ICT tools, though with slightly less certainty than their attitudes. While they acknowledge the usefulness of ICT and their proficiency in its application, the ranking indicates that there may still be areas for improvement, particularly in advanced digital competencies such as troubleshooting, multimedia content creation, and digital assessment tools.

Perception ranks third, with a WM of 4.13 (SD = 0.333), also interpreted as "Strongly Agree." This suggests that while teachers recognize the importance of ICT in enhancing instruction and student learning, their perception is slightly less positive compared to their attitudes and skills. The slight difference may indicate that while teachers are open to and capable of using ICT, some still hold reservations about its full effectiveness compared to traditional teaching methods.

Overall, the average weighted mean across all cognitive-affective factors is 4.34 (SD = 0.330), interpreted as "Strongly Agree." This indicates that teachers generally have a positive attitude, strong perceptions, and solid skills in ICT integration. However, the ranking differences suggest that while enthusiasm for ICT is high, continuous training and support in skill development may further strengthen teachers' confidence and ability to maximize technology in education.

ICT Integration using SAMR Model

This part of the study deals with the level of ICT integration of the English teacher using SAMR model.

Substitution

ICT integration at the substitution level allows educators to replace traditional tools with digital alternatives, improving accessibility and engagement without altering the core task. Table 12 shows the level of integration of teachers in terms of substitution.

Table 12. Substitution

Indicators	WM	SD	VI
1. Use ICTs (e.g. laptop, hand phone, Microsoft word) to prepare her lecture, assignments, and examinations	4.20	0.301	FE
2. Use digital taking note instead of a printed notebook.	4.40	0.321	FE
3. Use the PowerPoint presentation method to deliver lectures	4.10	0.293	E
4. Upload the teaching and learning materials on Facebook or other electronic sites/devices for students to access.	3.50	0.279	E
5. Refer students to electronic databases for reference materials instead of hard copy textbooks	3.40	0.283	E
6. When supporting her students, the teacher communicates to them using her cell phone.	3.90	0.281	E
7. When supporting the students, the teacher communicates to them through social media such as Facebook, Twitter, chat rooms, and discussion boards.	3.90	0.281	E
8. Have specific folders in her laptop to manage file of her students' works.	3.80	0.278	E
9. Record her lectures on CDs/other media and give them to her students	2.90	0.325	A

10. Take video/audio recordings of herself while lecturing and uses them in subsequent years to teach the same course to another cohort of students	3.00	0.314	A
Average Mean	3.71	0.296	E

Legend

4.20- 5.00 Fully Expert 2.60-3.39 Advance 1.00-1.79 Novice
 3.40- 4.19 Expert 1.80-2.59 Intermediate

The data in Table 12 highlights the extent to which teachers utilize ICT for substitution in their teaching practices. The highest-ranked indicator, with a weighted mean (WM) of 4.40 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.321, shows that teachers frequently use digital note-taking instead of printed notebooks. The second-ranked indicator, with a WM of 4.20 (SD = 0.301), reflects the use of ICT tools such as laptops, mobile phones, and Microsoft Word for preparing lectures, assignments, and examinations. The use of PowerPoint presentations for delivering lectures ranked third, with a WM of 4.10 (SD = 0.293).

Teachers' use of cell phones (WM = 3.90, SD = 0.281) and social media platforms (WM = 3.90, SD = 0.281) for student support ranked fourth. Maintaining specific folders on a laptop to manage student work received a WM of 3.80 (SD = 0.278), ranking sixth. The use of online platforms such as Facebook and other electronic sites to upload teaching materials ranked seventh, with a WM of 3.50 (SD = 0.279), followed by referring students to electronic databases instead of hard-copy textbooks, which ranked eighth with a WM of 3.40 (SD = 0.283).

The lowest-ranked indicators involve recording lectures for later use. Recording lectures on CDs or other media received a WM of 2.90 (SD = 0.325), while taking video or audio recordings of lectures for future cohorts received a WM of 3.00 (SD = 0.314), ranking ninth and tenth, respectively. The average mean of 3.71 (SD = 0.296) falls within the "Expert" category.

At the Substitution level, technology acts as a direct replacement for traditional tools without altering the task's functionality. For example, a teacher might replace a physical worksheet with a digital PDF version. A study by Bicalho et al. (2023) found that while this level introduces technology into the classroom, it often results in minimal pedagogical change, serving primarily to digitize existing practices.

Augmentation

By incorporating ICT to enhance traditional methods, augmentation enables teachers to increase efficiency and interactivity, fostering a more dynamic learning environment. Table 13 shows the level of integration of ICT in terms of augmentation.

Table 13. Augmentation

Indicators	WM	SD	VI
1. Highlighted text in the digital device with color and different font size.	4.20	0.301	FE
2. Use search engines (e.g. Google) to look for the reference to the teaching material	4.40	0.321	FE
3. Use the editorial tools in the word processor to correct grammatical errors in any documents	3.80	0.278	E
4. Use digital libraries (e.g. Digilib, MuLib) as a source of useful content for the lectures	2.30	0.410	A
5. Use Internet group lists to contact students in matters related to their academics	3.10	0.304	A

6. Provide feedback to students' reports, papers and assignments through their social media or email	3.20	0.295	A
7. Use bulk messaging to contact students in matters related to their academics.	3.60	0.277	E
Average Mean	3.51	0.312	A

The data in Table 13 presents teachers' use of ICT for augmentation in their teaching practices. The highest-ranked indicator, with a weighted mean (WM) of 4.40 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.321, shows that teachers frequently use search engines such as Google to look for references for teaching materials. The second-ranked indicator, with a WM of 4.20 (SD = 0.301), reflects the use of highlighted text in digital devices with different colors and font sizes to enhance readability and organization.

The use of editorial tools in word processors to correct grammatical errors ranked third, with a WM of 3.80 (SD = 0.278). The use of bulk messaging to contact students regarding academic matters ranked fourth, with a WM of 3.60 (SD = 0.277). Providing feedback on students' reports, papers, and assignments through social media or email ranked fifth, with a WM of 3.20 (SD = 0.295).

The use of Internet group lists to contact students in academic matters ranked sixth, with a WM of 3.10 (SD = 0.304). The lowest-ranked indicator, with a WM of 2.30 (SD = 0.410), is the use of digital libraries such as Digilib and MuLib as a source of useful content for lectures. The average mean of 3.51 (SD = 0.312) falls within the "Advanced" category.

The Augmentation stage involves technology replacing traditional tools with added functional improvements. For instance, using a word processor with spell-check features enhances the writing process beyond what is possible with pen and paper. Bicalho et al. (2023) observed that this level provides slight enhancements to learning experiences but does not fundamentally change the instructional approach.

Modification

At the modification stage, ICT transforms learning experiences by enabling significant task redesign, encouraging collaboration, creativity, and deeper understanding. Table 14 shows the level of integration of ICT in terms of modification.

Table 14. Modification

Indicators	WM	SD	VI
1. Ever combined audio, video, and text notes in presenting material using an application such as "movie maker"	3.70	0.277	E
2. Administer multiple choice questions for tests/examinations through google form or other devices.	3.50	0.279	E
3. Use Google Drive to manage and collect files of students' works.	3.50	0.279	E
4. Lecture modules in the discipline using e-learning platforms (e.g. MUELE, Edmodo).	2.00	0.462	I
5. Use open education resource to use group discussion facility (e.g. Blog, Social Media, Web).	2.70	0.350	A
6. Use note taking application such as "Sling Note, Google note" program to curate online sources.	2.60	0.364	A
7. Use video conferencing or Skype to teach students when the teacher not at the school.	2.60	0.364	A
Average Mean	2.94	0.339	A

The data in Table 14 presents teachers' use of ICT for modification in their teaching practices. The highest-ranked indicator, with a weighted mean (WM) of 3.70 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.277, shows that teachers frequently combine audio, video, and text notes in presenting material using applications such as Movie Maker. The second-ranked indicators, both with a WM of 3.50 (SD = 0.279), involve administering multiple-choice tests or examinations through Google Forms and using Google Drive to manage and collect student work.

The use of open educational resources for group discussions, such as blogs, social media, and web-based platforms, ranked fourth, with a WM of 2.70 (SD = 0.350). The use of note-taking applications like Sling Note and Google Note, along with video conferencing tools such as Skype for remote teaching, ranked fifth, both with a WM of 2.60 (SD = 0.364).

The lowest-ranked indicator, with a WM of 2.00 (SD = 0.462), is the use of e-learning platforms such as MUELE and Edmodo for lecture modules. The average mean of 2.94 (SD = 0.339) falls within the "Advanced" category, indicating that while teachers incorporate ICT in modifying their instructional practices, its application is not as widespread or fully integrated compared to other ICT uses.

Modification signifies a significant redesign of tasks enabled by technology. An example is students collaborating on a shared document in real-time, allowing for immediate feedback and collective editing. A scoping review by Blundell et al. (2022) highlighted that at this level, technology begins to transform learning activities, fostering collaboration and deeper engagement.

Redefinition

Through redefinition, ICT empowers educators to create entirely new learning experiences that were previously unimaginable, preparing students for the digital world with innovative, real-world applications. ICT integration in terms of redefinition is display in table 15.

Table 15. Redefinition

Indicators	WM	SD	VI
1. Include audio, video, and other interactive online platforms to use as the multimodal teaching material.	3.60	0.277	E
2. Share digital notebook or using a certain application to develop notetaking.	2.70	0.350	A
3. Create a multimodal task to make the instruction more real, interesting and challenging for students.	3.00	0.314	A
4. Use open education resources as my study materials (e.g. MOOC)	2.20	0.427	I
5. Use e-learning platforms (e.g. Near Pod, MOOC) to assess my students' learning	2.30	0.410	I
6. Use augmented reality when teaching.	2.90	0.325	A
7. Use electronic games when teaching.	3.00	0.314	A
Average Mean	2.81	0.345	A

The data in Table 15 presents teachers' use of ICT for redefinition in their teaching practices. The highest-ranked indicator, with a weighted mean (WM) of 3.60 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.277, shows that teachers frequently include audio, video, and other interactive online platforms as multimodal teaching materials. The second-ranked indicators, both with a WM of 3.00 (SD = 0.314), involve creating multimodal tasks to make instruction more engaging and using electronic games in teaching.

The use of augmented reality in teaching ranked fourth, with a WM of 2.90 (SD = 0.325). The use of digital notebooks or specific applications for notetaking ranked fifth, with a WM of 2.70 (SD =

0.350). The lowest-ranked indicators involve the use of e-learning platforms such as Nearpod and MOOCs for student assessment (WM = 2.30, SD = 0.410) and using open educational resources like MOOCs as study materials (WM = 2.20, SD = 0.427), ranking sixth and seventh, respectively.

The average mean of 2.81 (SD = 0.345) falls within the "Advanced" category, suggesting that while some redefinition strategies are adopted, their overall implementation remains at a developing stage.

At the Redefinition stage, technology makes it possible to create previously unthinkable new tasks. Students might, for instance, make interactive multimedia presentations and distribute them to a worldwide audience. According to Blundell et al. (2022), this stage facilitates creative teaching and learning methods and results in transforming educational experiences.

Summary on ICT Integration Using SAMR Model

Table 16 shows the summary of the weighted means of ICT integration using SAMR model.

Table 16. ICT Integration Using SAMR Model

Variables	WM	SD	VI
Substitute	3.71	0.296	E
Augmentation	3.51	0.312	A
Modification	2.94	0.339	A
Redefinition	2.81	0.345	A
Average Mean	3.24	0.323	A

The data in Table 16 presents the levels of ICT integration and engagement among teachers using the SAMR model. The highest-ranked dimension, with a weighted mean (WM) of 3.71 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.296, is Substitution, indicating that teachers most frequently use ICT to replace traditional methods without significant functional changes. This suggests that while ICT is widely utilized, it is primarily applied to replicate conventional teaching practices rather than transform them.

Augmentation ranks second, with a WM of 3.51 (SD = 0.312), showing that teachers integrate ICT with slight functional improvements, such as enhancing text with digital tools or using online resources for information retrieval. Modification, with a WM of 2.94 (SD = 0.339), ranks third, reflecting a moderate level of ICT transformation where teachers restructure traditional teaching methods through digital tools, such as using Google Forms for assessments or incorporating multimedia elements into lessons.

The lowest-ranked dimension is Redefinition, with a WM of 2.81 (SD = 0.345), indicating that teachers least frequently use ICT to create entirely new learning experiences that were previously impossible without technology. This suggests that advanced ICT-driven instructional strategies, such as augmented reality, e-learning platforms, and open educational resources, are not yet widely adopted.

With an overall average mean of 3.24 (SD = 0.323), the data suggests that ICT integration among teachers falls within the "Advanced" category, with a stronger emphasis on Substitution and Augmentation rather than higher-order transformation through Modification and Redefinition.

SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ICT ENGAGEMENT AND INTEGRATION USING SAMR MODEL

This section discusses significant relationships.

Table 17 reveals whether there is a significant relationship on the level of engagement in teaching-learning in terms of cognitive-affective factors and ICT integration through SAMR practices.

Table 17. ICT Engagement and Integration Using SAMR Model

	Computed r- value	Critical p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Attitude and SAMR Model	0.8809	0.008244	Reject Ho	Significant
Skills and SAMR Model	0.6975	0.036724	Reject Ho	Significant
Perception and SAMR Model	0.7462	0.016499	Reject Ho	Significant

@ 0.05 level of significance

The data presented in Table 17 examines the relationship between ICT engagement and integration using the SAMR Model in relation to attitude, skills, and perception. The results indicate that attitude has the strongest correlation with the SAMR Model, with an r-value of 0.8809 and a p-value of 0.008244, signifying a strong and significant relationship. This suggests that individuals with a positive attitude toward ICT are more likely to integrate it effectively using the SAMR framework. Similarly, ICT skills also demonstrate a significant positive relationship with the SAMR Model, as evidenced by an r-value of 0.6975 and a p-value of 0.036724. This indicates that higher ICT skills contribute to better integration, although the correlation is not as strong as that of attitude. Additionally, perception also plays a crucial role, with an r-value of 0.7462 and a p-value of 0.016499, further confirming a significant positive relationship. This means that individuals who perceive ICT positively are more likely to engage with and integrate it effectively using the SAMR Model. Since all p-values are below 0.05, these relationships are statistically significant, reinforcing the importance of fostering positive attitudes, enhancing skills, and improving perceptions toward ICT to maximize its integration.

ISSUES AND CONCERNS

This section deals with the issues and concerns encountered by the teachers in managing and resolving conflicts related to instruction.

Table 18 shows the indicators for the issues and concerns faced by teachers in managing and resolving conflicts in an instructional context.

Table 18. Issues and Concerns in ICT Integration and Engagement of English Teachers

Issues and Concerns	Frequency
1. Technical Issues and Maintenance - Frequent hardware and software problems, slow internet speeds, and system failures can disrupt lessons.	30
2. Lack of Infrastructure - lack the necessary ICT facilities such as computers, projectors, or stable internet connections.	28
3. Limited Teacher Training- some English teachers may not have adequate training in using ICT tools effectively in their lessons.	27
4. High Cost of Technology - Purchasing and maintaining ICT tools, software, and internet services can be expensive for schools.	21
5. Digital Divide - There is a gap between students who have access to technology at home and those who do not, creating inequalities in learning opportunities.	19
6. Resistance to Change -Some teachers and administrators may be reluctant to shift from traditional teaching methods to ICT-based approaches.	16

7. Time-Consuming Lesson Preparation - Teachers may need extra time to prepare ICT-integrated lessons, which can be challenging with an already heavy workload.	15
8. Difficulty in Assessing Student Performance - Some teachers find it challenging to evaluate students' learning outcomes when using digital platforms instead of traditional assessments.	14
9. Distraction in Learning - Students may use ICT tools for non-educational purposes, such as playing games or browsing social media, instead of focusing on lessons.	8
10. Cybersecurity and Privacy Concerns - Risks such as data breaches, online bullying, and exposure to inappropriate content pose challenges for both teachers and students.	6

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in English teaching presents several issues and concerns that impact both educators and students. One of the most pressing challenges is technical issues and maintenance, with frequent hardware malfunctions, software problems, and slow internet connections disrupting lessons (30 occurrences). Frequent hardware and software problems, slow internet speeds, and system failures can disrupt lessons. Abdullayeva (2024) notes that technical problems, such as outdated software and restricted access to updates, play a significant role in hindering complete ICT integration in teaching English.

Additionally, a lack of infrastructure, such as computers, projectors, and stable internet access, further hinders the effective implementation of ICT in classrooms (28 occurrences). The absence of necessary ICT facilities, such as computers, projectors, or stable internet connections, hampers effective integration. Cao et al. (2023) highlight that inadequate infrastructure is a critical barrier to ICT integration in English language teaching in China.

Another major concern is the limited training of teachers in using ICT tools effectively, as some educators may struggle to integrate technology into their lessons due to insufficient professional development (27 occurrences). Some English teachers may not have adequate training in using ICT tools effectively in their lessons. Abdullayeva (2024) emphasizes that insufficient training is a significant challenge, hindering teachers' ability to integrate ICT effectively.

The high cost of technology also plays a significant role, as purchasing and maintaining ICT tools, software, and internet services can be expensive, making it difficult for schools to keep up with technological advancements (21 occurrences). Purchasing and maintaining ICT tools, software, and internet services can be expensive for schools. Abdullayeva (2024) mentions that insufficient funding is a critical challenge in integrating ICT into English language teaching.

Moreover, the digital divide creates disparities among students, as some have access to technology at home while others do not, leading to inequalities in learning opportunities (19 occurrences). There is a gap between students who have access to technology at home and those who do not, creating inequalities in learning opportunities. Cao et al. (2023) discuss that the digital divide significantly impacts students' access to ICT resources, affecting their learning outcomes.

Resistance to change is another obstacle, with some teachers and administrators preferring traditional teaching methods over ICT-based approaches, which can slow down the adoption of innovative teaching strategies (16 occurrences). Some teachers and administrators may be reluctant to shift from traditional teaching methods to ICT-based approaches. Abdullayeva (2024) identifies resistance to change as a barrier to effective ICT integration in English language teaching.

Furthermore, the time-consuming nature of lesson preparation using ICT tools adds to teachers' workload, making it difficult to integrate technology into their already busy schedules (15

occurrences). Teachers may need extra time to prepare ICT-integrated lessons, which can be challenging with an already heavy workload. Abdullayeva (2024) notes that teachers' workloads, including marking assignments and preparing materials, negatively affect ICT integration.

Assessing student performance through digital platforms is another challenge, as some educators find it difficult to measure learning outcomes effectively without traditional assessment methods (14 occurrences). Some teachers find it challenging to evaluate students' learning outcomes when using digital platforms instead of traditional assessments. Cao et al. (2023) highlight that assessment concerns are among the challenges teachers face in integrating ICT into English language teaching.

Furthermore, learning distractions are a problem as students may abuse ICT resources for non-educational activities like social media surfing or gaming instead of paying attention to their courses (8 instances). Instead of concentrating on lectures, students may utilize ICT equipment for non-educational activities like social media surfing or gaming.

Lastly, cybersecurity and privacy concerns pose risks for both teachers and students, including data breaches, online bullying, and exposure to inappropriate content (6 occurrences). Risks such as data breaches, online bullying, and exposure to inappropriate content pose challenges for both teachers and students. Abdullayeva (2024) mentions that cybersecurity and privacy concerns are among the challenges teachers face in integrating ICT into English language teaching.

Overall, even though integrating ICT into English instruction has the potential to improve student learning, these problems need to be resolved to guarantee fair and efficient use. In order to optimize the advantages of ICT while reducing its disadvantages, schools must make investments in improved infrastructure, offer sufficient training for teachers, and set clear policies.

Chapter 3

SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter dealt with the summary, findings, conclusions, and recommendations. The summary restates the major problems and sub problems of the study. The findings are based upon the gathered data; the conclusions were based upon the findings and the recommendations were carefully taught out based upon the gathered data.

SUMMARY

This research assessed the level of ICT engagement in terms of cognitive-affective factors and the extent of ICT integration practices of English teacher of Basak Elementary School.

The study was limited to the following areas of concern: related information of the teachers' age and gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in the service, and related trainings, seminars, and workshops attended; level of ICT engagement in terms of cognitive-affective factors namely: attitude, perception and skills; extent of ICT integration practices using SAMR model. The researcher made use of the descriptive – correlational method of research with the use of adapted and modified questionnaire as the main tool in the gathering of relevant data.

FINDINGS

The following were the main findings.

The majority of the teachers were between the ages of 21 and 30, female, married, with 15 units in master's degree, have served 1-5 years and have attended school level training and seminars.

The level of ICT engagement of the teachers in terms of cognitive-affective factors have sensed a strong agreement especially on their attitudes towards ICT. It clearly shows that they fully embrace and actively engage with ICT in their teaching. As to the extent of ICT integration using SAMR Model suggests that ICT integration among teachers falls within the "Advanced" category,

with a stronger emphasis on Substitution and Augmentation rather than higher-order transformation through Modification and Redefinition.

The study found a substantial correlation between conflict management styles in instruction and the school performance. The issues and concerns encountered by the respondents in integrating ICT are the following: technical issues and maintenance, lack of infrastructure, limited teacher training, high cost of technology, digital divide, resistance to change, time-consuming lesson preparation, distraction in learning and cybersecurity and privacy concerns.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that ICT engagement in terms of cognitive-affective factors and ICT integration using SAMR model have a significant relationship with each other.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations was offered: Implementation of the training plan for English teachers be implemented for the next school year.

Chapter 4

OUTPUT OF THE STUDY

RATIONALE

In today's digital age, integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into English language teaching is essential for enhancing instructional delivery, student engagement, and overall learning outcomes. Many educators, however, face challenges in effectively utilizing digital tools due to limited training and resources. A well-structured training plan on ICT engagement and integration equips English teachers with the necessary skills to incorporate technology into their teaching practices. This initiative not only enhances their pedagogical effectiveness but also fosters a more interactive and student-centered learning environment. By developing digital literacy and competence, teachers can create innovative lessons that cater to diverse learning styles, ultimately improving students' language acquisition and communication skills.

Furthermore, empowering English teachers with ICT skills ensures that they stay relevant in an increasingly technology-driven education landscape. The training will introduce them to practical applications such as digital lesson planning, online assessment tools, and interactive multimedia resources. It will also provide strategies to address common technological barriers, ensuring seamless integration of ICT in the classroom. This professional development initiative aligns with global educational standards, promoting a forward-thinking approach to language instruction. By fostering confidence and proficiency in ICT usage, the program will enable English teachers to enhance their instructional methods, boost student engagement, and optimize learning experiences.

OBJECTIVES

This training plan will hopefully:

1. Enhance Digital Competency: Equip English teachers with essential ICT skills for effective integration into lesson planning, instruction, and assessment.
2. Promote Interactive Teaching Strategies: Train teachers to use digital tools and online resources to create engaging and student-centered English language lessons.
3. Address Technological Challenges: Provide solutions and strategies for overcoming common ICT-related barriers in the classroom, ensuring smooth technology integration.

Scheme of Implementation

This output will be submitted to the District Supervisor for preliminary approval and be endorsed to the Division Office for validation and for deliberation and possible appropriate action.

Target Clientele

The clientele of the training plan are the English teachers of Basak Elementary School.

TRAINING PLAN ON ICT ENGAGEMENT AND INTEGRATION

School Year 2024-2025

1. Proposal Brief

Activity Proponent	MERLYN P. LOMOCSO
Target Participants	English Teachers of Basak Elementary School
Number of Teachers	30
Proposed Venue	Basak Elementary School
Total Proposed Budget	Php 25,000.00
Proposed Continuing Professional Education credits units (if any)	N/A
Registration Fee	N/A

2. Activity Background and Rationale

Rationale

In today's digital age, integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into English language teaching is essential for enhancing instructional delivery, student engagement, and overall learning outcomes. Many educators, however, face challenges in effectively utilizing digital tools due to limited training and resources. A well-structured training plan on ICT engagement and integration equips English teachers with the necessary skills to incorporate technology into their teaching practices. This initiative not only enhances their pedagogical effectiveness but also fosters a more interactive and student-centered learning environment. By developing digital literacy and competence, teachers can create innovative lessons that cater to diverse learning styles, ultimately improving students' language acquisition and communication skills.

Furthermore, empowering English teachers with ICT skills ensures that they stay relevant in an increasingly technology-driven education landscape. The training will introduce them to practical applications such as digital lesson planning, online assessment tools, and interactive multimedia resources. It will also provide strategies to address common technological barriers, ensuring seamless integration of ICT in the classroom. This professional development initiative aligns with global educational standards, promoting a forward-thinking approach to language instruction. By fostering confidence and proficiency in ICT usage, the program will enable English teachers to enhance their instructional methods, boost student engagement, and optimize learning experiences.

Thus, this training plan is designed for English teachers of Basak Elementary School.

3. Program Description

This is a 2-day training seminar which will help teachers enhance their engagement and integration of ICT in their English instruction. The modality to be used is a face-to-face seminar which will be conducted in Basak Elementary School. The target participants for this

undertaking are the 30 English teachers of Basak Elementary School.

4. Target Participant's Description

The target participants for this training workshop are the English teachers of Basak Elementary School.

5. Program Learning Objectives

The program aims to:

1. **Enhance Digital Competency:** Equip English teachers with essential ICT skills for effective integration into lesson planning, instruction, and assessment.
2. **Promote Interactive Teaching Strategies:** Train teachers to use digital tools and online resources to create engaging and student-centered English language lessons.
3. **Address Technological Challenges:** Provide solutions and strategies for overcoming common ICT-related barriers in the classroom, ensuring smooth technology integration.

Content	Topics	Objectives	Suggested Activities	Duration	Expected Output
Introduction to ICT in English Instruction	-Importance of ICT in modern education -Overview of digital tools for English instruction -Setting learning goals for ICT integration	Understand the significance of ICT in English instruction and set goals for integration.	Interactive lecture, group discussions, and brainstorming activities.	2 hours	A personal action plan for ICT integration in the classroom
Digital Literacy and Online Safety	- Basics of digital literacy for educators - Cybersecurity and responsible digital citizenship - Managing digital resources effectively	Develop digital literacy skills and ensure safe online teaching practices.	Hands-on training, case studies, and role-playing scenarios.	2 hours	A guide on online safety practices and responsible digital citizenship.
Interactive Teaching Tools	- Exploring Learning Management Systems (LMS) (e.g., Google Classroom, Moodle) - Using interactive whiteboards and presentation tools (e.g., Padlet, Jamboard) - Creating engaging multimedia presentations	Utilize various digital tools to enhance interactive learning experiences.	Demonstration, hands-on workshops, and peer collaboration.	2 hours	A sample lesson using an LMS and interactive tools.
Gamification and Online Assessment	- Gamification in English learning (e.g., Kahoot, Quizizz) - Designing formative and summative assessments online - Analyzing student performance using digital tools	Apply gamification strategies and digital assessments to engage students.	Hands-on practice with gamification platforms, discussion, and peer feedback.	2 hrs.	A gamified quiz or assessment plan using an online tool.
Content Creation and Digital Storytelling	- Creating digital lesson plans and interactive worksheets - Podcasting and video storytelling for language learning - Tools for animation and visual storytelling (e.g., Canva, Powtoon)	Create digital content and storytelling resources to enhance language learning.	Hands-on practice with digital tools, multimedia production, and peer review.	2 hrs.	A short podcast or digital story for English instruction.
Collaborative Learning and Virtual Classrooms	- Implementing collaborative learning through ICT (e.g., Google Docs, Microsoft Teams) - Managing virtual classrooms effectively - Engaging students through discussion forums and blogs	Foster collaboration through virtual classroom tools and digital platforms.	Simulated virtual classroom activities, group work, and online discussions.	2 hrs.	A collaborative activity plan using ICT tools.
AI and Emerging Technologies in English Instruction	- Understanding the role of AI in education - Using AI tools for language learning (e.g., ChatGPT, Grammarly, speech-to-text applications) - Ethical considerations of AI in education	Explore the role of AI and emerging technologies in language instruction.	Demonstrations of AI tools, discussions on ethical considerations, and hands-on practice.	2 hrs.	A classroom integration plan using AI tools.
Practical Application and Lesson Demonstration	- Developing a lesson plan integrating ICT tools - Peer review and feedback sessions - Certification and action plan for continued professional development	Apply acquired ICT skills by designing and demonstrating an ICT-integrated lesson.	Lesson planning, peer evaluation, and constructive feedback sessions.	2 hrs.	A fully developed lesson plan incorporating ICT tools and a demonstration.

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